

The principle of *jura novit arbiter* and *jura novit curia*

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Abstract.

The principle of *jura novit arbiter* or *jura novit tribunus* is a projection of the doctrine of *jura novit curia* onto international arbitration proceedings, free from the peculiarities of national legislation. The significance of the application of this principle lies in the ability of the arbitral tribunal to take part in establishing the content of the applicable rules of law. Taking into account the peculiarities of international arbitration, *jura novit arbiter* is significantly limited in order to protect the interests of the disputing parties. However, such a restriction has both positive and negative legal consequences.

Key words: arbitration, principle of jura novit curia, jura novit curia, panel of arbitrators, legal qualifications, applicable law

INTRODUCTION

It is widely recognized that the will of the parties plays a determinant role in international commercial arbitration. The aim of this book is to investigate to what extent the arbitral tribunal may nevertheless develop its own legal reasoning. An independent legal reasoning will not necessarily be based on the will of the parties as manifested in the terms of the contract, in the law chosen in the contract or in the legal arguments presented by the parties in the proceedings.

As an illustration of the questions that the book aims at answering, the following can be mentioned:

- (i) Assume that an arbitral tribunal is called upon to decide whether a sales contract has been breached, and, if it ascertains that the contract was breached, to determine the amount of damages owed by the defaulting party. Assume that, during the proceeding, the claimant claims that the contract was breached because performance was late. Having heard the evidence, however, the arbitral tribunal decides that the contract was breached because the goods were not in conformity with the specifications. May the tribunal order reimbursement of damages (as requested), on a basis different from the basis that was pleaded (i.e., non-conformity instead of delay)?
- (ii) Assume that the dispute regards the breach of a shares purchase agreement. The seller argues that its liability is limited to the circumstances described in the Representations and Warranties contained in the agreement. The circumstance invoked by the purchaser is not included in the Representations and Warranties. The purchaser claims that the seller has breached a duty to inform

MATERIALS AND METHODS. As materials for the study, we used international treaties regulating the establishment of the content of the applicable law, the practice of international commercial and investment arbitration, demonstrating ways of establishing the limits of the arbitral tribunal's free discretion and the corresponding the consequences of limiting the principle of *jura novit arbiter*, as well as the works of Russian and foreign scientists. The methodological basis of the study is made up of general scientific and special legal methods.

The role and importance of the principle of *jura novit arbiter* and *jura novit curia*

The principle of *jura novit arbiter* or *jura novit tribunus* is an analogue of the doctrine of *jura novit curia* in international arbitration, free from the peculiarities of national law. The importance of its application in international arbitration lies in the powers of the arbitral tribunal to participate in determining the content of the applicable law. Taking into account the characteristics of international arbitration, serious restrictions are placed on the principle of *jura novit arbiter* in order to protect the rights and interests of the disputing parties. However, restrictions have positive and negative legal effects.¹

Within the framework of determining the content of the applicable court, the acceptable limits of the exercise of discretionary powers of arbitrators differ in different legal procedures, which can be clearly seen at the stage of annulment and recognition and enforcement of substantive law arbitration decisions. The reason is that it is the state courts that review arbitration awards, so complete uniformity in this matter is not possible. Therefore, despite the idea of "delocalization and procedural liberalization" in arbitration, some issues remain to a certain extent in the sphere of national regulation.

In such conditions, the need to create universal procedural guarantees and rules called *lex mercatoria arbitralis* naturally arose in the doctrine. One of its manifestations is the principle of *jura novit arbiter*, which is a projection of the doctrine of *jura novit curia* to the international arbitration discussion, free from the peculiarities of national legislation, that is, it is a product of harmonization. Projecting the *jura novit curia* principle applied in state courts to international arbitration is of great importance. First, if the principle did not apply in arbitration,

¹ Born G. International commercial arbitration. 2nd ed. Alphen aan den Rijn: Wolters Kluwer Law & Business. 2014. 4408 p.

the arbitral tribunal would be bound only by the legal arguments, materials and interpretations offered by the parties.²

In such conditions, the risk of errors in the application and interpretation of legal norms increases significantly. Second, the doctrine of *jura novit tribunus* allows to prevent relevant unfair practices without violating the basic principles of international arbitration. Fourthly, the application of the principle helps to increase the guarantee of the execution of the decision in other legal documents, because it gives the arbitrators the right to appeal to the rules of public order, the extreme imperative rules of the parties.³

However, due to the specific characteristics of international arbitration, the use of *jura novit tribunus* should be limited, the purpose of narrowing the discretion of the arbitral tribunal is to ensure legal predictability and certainty of arbitration. The authors concluded that the main universal means of limiting the use of *jura novit arbitrator* are other principles of international commercial arbitration:

- *ne ultra petita*,
- due process
- expediency and efficiency.

However, as it turns out, restrictions are a double-edged sword: on the one hand, they allow preliminary assessment of the outcome of arbitration proceedings, the risks of annulment or recognition and enforcement, and also save time, on the other hand, they may create a different kind of legal uncertainty.

Ne ultra petita

² Alberti C.P. *Iura Novit Curia in International Commercial Arbitration - How much justice do you want?*. – International Arbitration and International Commercial Law: Synergy, Convergence and Evolution. The Hague: Kluwer Law International. 2011. P. 3-32.

³ Capper M. 2014. Proving the Contents of the Applicable Substantive Law(s). – *The application of substantive law by international arbitrators. Institute Dossier XI*. Paris: ICC. P. 31-54.

The *ne ultra petita* principle is one of the basic principles of international arbitration. Failure to do so may result in termination (34(1), (2)(a)(iii) of the UNCITRAL Model Law on International Commercial Arbitration 1985). In order to analyze the interaction between the doctrines of *jura novit arbiter* and *ne ultra petita*, we will first turn to its practice and consider its essence.

The Italian court clearly defined in which case the principle of *ne ultra petita* is violated: the parties have the right to independently determine the subject of the dispute, their requirements, this right belongs only to them, therefore, if the arbitral tribunal decides more than the required amount, the parties have not announced regardless, it interferes with their absolute powers.

Thus, the extent to which *jura novit arbitrator* can be exercised is limited by parameters set by the parties, such as the amount of the claim, which means that arbitrators cannot award a party more than he has requested by interpreting the court's provision broadly, or the parties *ex lon* will not resolve the dispute on other legal grounds. In essence, arbitrators are empowered to exercise their discretionary powers as long as they do not violate the autonomy of the will of the parties..

The principle of *ne ultra petita* aims to ensure legal certainty and predictability of arbitration proceedings and their results. However, it should be taken into account that there are no clear criteria for the implementation of *ne ultra petita*: it is necessary to take into account the situation when determining the existence or not of its violation. For example, the *ne ultra petita* principle, given the arbitral tribunal's wide discretionary powers, is not violated if the claimant's claim for protection is not legally supported. However, if the claimant has provided a legal justification for the legal remedies he has chosen, then, as a rule, no other grounds for accepting the arbitral award can be given, because in this case the arbitral award

will violate the provisions of the *ne ultra petita* principle. is accepted without violation.⁴

We give an example from the practice of the Supreme Court of Finland, *Werfen Austria GmbH v. Polar Electro Europe B.V.* explained that the arbitral tribunal did not violate the rights of the parties in the exercise of its discretionary powers, because the legal nature of the agreement was controversial and the parties could not be dissatisfied with the decision under any circumstances.

Due process

The application of the doctrine of *jura novit arbiter*, as well as the main principle of the proper conduct of arbitration proceedings, is due process, one of whose components is limited to the right to be heard. The arbitral tribunal must inform the parties about the possibility of applying another rule unknown to them, creating a different interpretation, and must ensure the right to state their position on the issue. The requirement to comply with due process is contained in Article 34.2(a)(ii) of the New York Convention, UNCITRAL Model Law. Similar provisions are contained in Article IX(1)(b) of the 1961 European Convention on Foreign Trade Arbitration.

The mechanism of interplay between *jura novit arbiter* and due process is that the decision must be analyzed in terms of respecting the rights of the party in question to avoid a deadlock in favor of the litigant. It should be noted that the practice of applying this principle of appropriate arbitration is ambiguous: the consequence of its violation is not always the annulment of the award or the refusal

⁴ Dimolitsa A. The equivocal power of the arbitrators to introduce *ex officio* new issues of law. – *ASA Bull.* 2009. Vol. 27. Issue 2. P. 427-440. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.54648/asab2009042>

to recognize and enforce it. Let us consider three different aspects of the interaction between the principles of *jura novit curia* and the right to be heard:⁵

1) the arbitrators informed the parties about the application of legal norms and gave them the opportunity to express their legal positions, so the rights of the parties were respected and there were no risks related to the validity and enforcement of the decision of the arbitration court;

2) if the arbitration court did not give the parties the opportunity to familiarize themselves with the new legal grounds that are the basis for making a decision, the right to a trial is violated and the decision of the arbitration court may be challenged or not recognized;

3) if the arbitrators did not inform the parties about the application of new legal norms, the changing interpretation of the norm, if the rights of the parties were violated, but taking into account all the circumstances of the case and the progress of the case, the parties turn to them in the arbitration proceedings could have foreseen what they would do, so the arbitral award is valid and enforceable (the foreseeability test).

In any legal proceeding, violation of a party's right to be heard is an absolute ground for setting aside an arbitral award. Thus, the Swedish Court of Appeal overturned the decision of the Stockholm Chamber of Commerce Arbitration Institute because the decision was based on legal norms that neither party referred to.⁶

Expediency and efficiency

⁵ Fouchard Gaillard & Goldman on International Commercial Arbitration. Ed. by E. Gaillard and J. Savage. 1999. Alphen aan den Rijn: Kluwer Law International. 1280 p.

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The third type of restriction on the implementation of the principle of *jura novit arbiter* is expressed in the requirement imposed on the arbitration court for the speed and efficiency of the arbitration proceedings (expediency and efficiency).⁷

In order to justify the need to consider this type of restriction separately and to show its interaction with the principle of *jura novit arbiter*, we simulate an arbitration: For example, the parties have their own legal opinion on the application, interpretation, etc. presented their positions. However, the arbitrator does not agree with all the rules, so he brings other legal arguments and informs the disputing parties about it, giving them the opportunity to get acquainted and give an opinion on the admissibility of their application. Then other similar *sua sponte* proposals appear, indicating the need to start again to familiarize the parties with new legal rules. At the same time, taking into account the need to ensure the optimal speed of consideration of the case, the obligation to give the parties an opportunity to express their views should be respected. This raises the important and complex issue of ensuring the correct implementation of arbitration in the context of the regular emergence of new legal frameworks and limited time. Thus, an arbitrator can never make an award if he continuously submits to the parties for consideration the reasons for an *ex officio* award"

The limitation in the form of the principle of expediency and efficiency is aimed at optimal use of the time of arbitration and reducing the costs of its implementation. However, time limitations in the application of *jura novit arbiter* may adversely affect the substantive part of the arbitral award. Therefore, the need to maintain a balance between *jura novit* principles is a priority.

⁷ Ly F. *Conflicts of Law in International Arbitration-An Overview*. Munich: European Law Publishers. 2011. 16 p.

The Latin *jura novit curia* literally means: "The court knows the law." Romano-Germanic legal systems interpret this phrase as the right of the court to justify its decisions without relying on the legal arguments offered by the parties. General legal systems, as a rule, reject this principle by defining a limited role for the court in the adversarial process. Since arbitration is very specific, the choice of law by the parties does not decide the application of the principle of *jura novit curia* in the context of arbitration.⁸

Therefore, the arbitrator, should this principle be applied in the case at hand, and if so, to what extent? Here it is recommended to focus on the interaction of this principle with two main rules of arbitration: party autonomy and uniformity in the application of the chosen law. These aspects greatly influence arbitrators in determining the degree of discretion they can exercise in applying the rule of *jura novit curia*.

The above problem cannot be solved by simply referring to the fundamental rights of the parties. This is due to two main reasons.

First, national procedural law rules do not apply to arbitration. Most arbitral institutions, if chosen by the contracting parties, follow predetermined rules of procedure that override the procedural rules of a particular country. In other words, the rules of procedural law chosen by the parties do not replace the procedural rules included in the relevant arbitration rules.⁹

Based on this, some arbitral institutions independently establish special rules: "Unless the parties have agreed otherwise in writing ... the Arbitrator ... at his discretion ... is necessary or expedient has the right to take the actions it deems

⁸ Ly F. *Conflicts of Law in International Arbitration-An Overview*. Munich: European Law Publishers. 2011. 16 p.

⁹ Jarvin S. *The Sources and Limits of the Arbitrator's Powers*. – *Arbitration International*. 1986. Vol. 2. Issue 2. P. 140- 163. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1093/arbitration/2.2.140>

appropriate. Including, the arbitration court itself decides whether or not (and to what extent) it can take the initiative in determining the relevant facts, as well as the laws or legal documents applicable to the arbitration on the nature of the dispute and the arbitration agreement" (27) , Articles 29). Arbitration Rules of the China International Economic and Trade Arbitration Commission). However, most arbitral tribunals, including the International Court of Arbitration, have not developed rules on the application of the principle of *jura novit curia*.¹⁰

Second, arbitration (we repeat) has a completely different legal nature than litigation in state court. For example, Article 46 of the English Arbitration Act 1966 states that the arbitral tribunal must decide the dispute "in accordance with the law chosen by the parties" or "on such other considerations as may be agreed upon by them or determined by the court". Thus, the question of the extent to which the parties can change the scope of the arbitrator's powers has not yet been resolved, as the rule of *jura novit curia*, in particular, applies to the judicial sphere.

At this point, it is worth noting that the inclusion of arbitration clauses in contracts has become a common practice and has led to the emergence of the stable phrase "midnight clause". Its meaning is that the negotiators formulate the content of the reservation using simple phrases, when all other terms have already been determined. As a rule, when concluding contracts, they first of all try to agree on the volume of products or services, their prices, terms of performance of obligations, the order of delivery and payment, and the formation of an arbitration clause.

Conflicting opinions of national courts on this issue may lead to additional problems. Thus, there are two opposing approaches: the courts either confirm the jurisdiction of the arbitration by applying the principle of *jura novit curia*, and the

¹⁰ Kurkela M.S. Due process in arbitration: a Finnish perspective. – Journal of International Arbitration. 2004. Vol. 21. Issue 2. P. 221-225.

arbitrators determine that they are not bound by the legal positions of the parties or do not recognize the rights. Arbitrators must follow the principle of *jura novit curia* during the proceedings. Currently, there seems to be no consensus on the practice of applying the studied principle in arbitration. To complicate matters, most arbitration clauses are drafted in a sketchy, template-based manner, and not all parties are willing to spend the extra time and money to agree on all aspects of the application of the *jura novit curia* principle, which may depend on: Arbitrators' specific issues or qualifications, as well as experience applying the law chosen by the parties. Perhaps the best solution for arbitral institutions is to include relevant provisions in their rules. Such an approach would at least provide some certainty to the parties, who would then be able to choose whether to depart from the established rules, having regard to the full circumstances of their case and their level of confidence in the jury. However, until such rules are developed, this old Latin principle will cause headaches for both practicing lawyers and judges.

CONCLUSION

As a result of the study, the authors came to the following conclusions.

1. The application of the principle of *jura novit arbiter* in international arbitration is subject to limitation in order to ensure the rights and legitimate interests of the disputing parties. Determined that The main instruments limiting the discretion of the arbitration tribunal are the principles of arbitration proceedings:

1) *ne ultra petita*, 2) *due process* and 3) *expediency and efficiency*.

2. Although it is necessary to establish the permissible limits of application of the principle of *jura novit arbiter*, limiting the discretionary powers of arbitrators can lead to legal uncertainty and unpredictability of arbitration proceedings (see below).

3. By virtue of the *ne ultra petita* principle, the arbitrators are bound by the remedies requested by the parties. There are exceptions to this rule, but there is no clarity in their application: when arbitrators have the corresponding right and when they do not.

3. Compliance with the due process principle is aimed at limiting the discretion of arbitrators by providing the parties opportunities to comment on issues explored *sua sponte*. If a particular interpretation of the applicable law is predictable, the corresponding obligation disappears. However, predictability is an evaluative category. The presence or absence of foreseeability is always resolved from the point of view of a particular court already at the stage of challenging or bringing in execution of the decision. In different legal systems under the same circumstances, the court may come to opposite conclusions on this issue.

4. The limiter in the form of the principle of expediency and efficiency is aimed at optimal use of the time of arbitration proceedings and reducing the costs of its implementation. However, time restrictions in the application of *jura novit arbiter* may have a negative effect on the substantive part of the arbitral award: essential aspects of the application of substantive law may be distorted, so the need to maintain a balance between the principles of *jura novit arbiter* and expediency and efficiency takes priority.

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